

Table 2. Yields of Mahsuri and Sona Mahsuri, Assam, India.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (kg/1.6 m ² plot)
Mahsuri	98	1
Sona Mahsuri	92	1

Two rows of 28 hills of each variety, divided by one row of susceptible check Pusa 2-21, were grown. Leaf Bl was scored by *The standard evaluation system for rice*. Neck Bl was recorded as percent affected panicles on 10 random hills. Yield was measured at a B1-free site.

Sona Mahsuri was moderately resistant to both neck Bl and leaf Bl (Table 1). Mahsuri was susceptible to leaf Bl and highly susceptible to neck Bl. Grain yields were on a par, but Sona Mahsuri matured 1 wk earlier than Mahsuri (Table 2). □

Screening new rice selections for reaction to major diseases

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We evaluated 18 stabilized lines from the rice improvement program and 18 released cultivars for leaf blast (Bl), neck Bl, sheath rot (ShR), and grain

discoloration (Gld) at the Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, (hot spot for B1 disease in rice) during 1986 wet season.

Selections from Pusa 150/IR36 and Pusa 150/IM 1 were resistant to leaf B1 (see table). Neck B1 infection was lowest in IR20, Karuna, and Jaya.

Selections from Jaya/Mahsuri were free of ShR infection. Maximum infection was in Pragathi and selections of Jaya/Type 3.

Jaya, IR20, and Jaya/ Mahsuri derivatives had the most Gld. Mahsuri, Intan Gowri, and Prakash had none.

Karuna and selections from Pusa 150/IM 1 showed combined tolerance for all four biotic stresses. □

Incidence of leaf B1, neck B1, ShR, and Gld. Ponnampet, Karnataka, India, 1986 wet season.

Entry	Leaf blast ^a	Neck B1 incidence (%)	ShR infection (%)	Gld (% affected)
Pusa 150/IR36	0	44.1	3.3	5.0
Pusa 150/IM-1	0	22.2	23.0	1.0
Karuna	0	10.2	6.8	1.0
Mahsuri	1	46.8	14.5	0.0
Intan Gowri	1	52.9	23.5	0.0
Jaya	1	14.0	19.8	25.0
Intan mutant 1	1		Wiped out by neck Bl	
IR20	2	7.4	9.3	25.0
Pusa 150/Tellahamsa	2	29.6	4.3	5.0
Jaya/Type 3	2	70.2	36.2	5.0
Mandya Vijaya	2		Wiped out by Bl	
Puspha	2	17.0	13.2	1.0
IET7031/Mangala	3	74.1	6.9	11.0
Pusa 150/Sona Mashuri	3	81.9	4.6	1.0
Nandi	3	87.0	5.7	1.0
Mahsuri/IR36	3	77.6	22.4	5.0
Prakash	4	33.7	18.6	0.0
Rasi	4		Wiped out by Bl	
Jaya/Basmati	4	55.8	1.9	5.0
Mandya Vani	5	45.1	31.4	10.0
ES18	5		Wiped out by Bl	
Jaya/Mahsuri	5	68.8	0.0	20.0
Jaya/IET7031	5		Wiped out by Bl	
Madhu	6		Wiped out by Bl	
Pragathi	6	41.9	39.6	10.0
Naga	6	76.2	20.6	1.0
Mangala	7		Wiped out by Bl	
IET7031/Tellahamsa	7	60.9	23.2	5.0
Sharavathi	7	72.1	27.9	1.0
Jaya/ Halubbulu	7		Wiped out by Bl	
Pusa 150/Basmati	7		Wiped out by Bl	
Intan	9	10.2 ^b	2.6 ^b	2.0 ^b
Tellahamsa	9		Wiped out by Bl	
Mahsuri/Doddy	9		Wiped out by Bl	
Karikagga/Halybbulu	9		Wiped out by Bl	
Arkavathi	9		Wiped out by Bl	

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 0-9. ^bFrom side tillers.

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Bacterial blight (BB) development in rice varieties and screening tests

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Genetic resistance appears to be the only feasible method of managing BB in the tropics and subtropics. In most screening tests, leaves are clip-inoculated with the local isolate of the pathogen at maximum tillering stage, with disease rated 15 d after inoculation (DAI). Total uniformity in the stage of plant growth, vigor, microclimate, amount of inoculum applied, and the mechanism of disease development in test varieties is difficult to achieve.

We evaluated inoculated plants against a wider spectrum of environmental conditions by rating disease in test varieties twice—15 and 35 DAI.

Some varieties expressed the maximum measurable response to *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

Disease reactions 15 and 35 DAI. Faizabad District, U.P., India.

Representative test varieties	Disease-score ^a		Type of reaction ^b	Varieties (no.)
	15 DAI	35 DAI		
Anjani III, Bishunbhog, Damodar, IR20, Randhuri, Zeerabatti	1	1	R	7
Chinidardi, Dehradun (Mota), Dhurigabha, Gallor, Gajraj, Kala Namak	1	3	MR (SB)	11
Katri, Loungchoor, Rambhog, Saraya, Sita, Surajpankhi 374	3	3	MR	10
Chameli	1	5	MS (VSB)	1
Beni, Benideoria, Gaurea, Mutmuri, Pankhali, Shyamzsera	3	5	MS (SB)	24
Adamchini, Amgandh, Badshah Pasand, Bhagalpuri, Ramjas	5	5	MS	29
Agwar, Bilaspur, Delha, Dadhaha, Sonachoor, FRG10	3	7	S (VSB)	6
Ashahniya, Basahwa, Dudaha, Jaisuria, Lalkibhadai, Sumokhan	5	7	S (SB)	13
Bajri, Bakki, Karhan, Kotabasmati, Mirchbooti, Motibadam	7	7	S	13
Champa (C), Kalamdan, Mutra, Sukhwan, Tinpakhiya, Agtahwa (FD)	5	9	HS (VSB)	9
Gheebhat, Kalakand, Karnya, Kashi P.D., Madhukar, Ramkajra	7	9	HS (SB)	11
Anand, Anjana, Bindibali, Bindikali, Gajgaur, TN1	9	9	HS	30

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980). ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible, SB = slow blighting, VSB = very slow blighting.

infection within 15 DAI; others took more time (see table).

The results indicate the limitations of recording observations only at 15 DAI. It is possible to divide reaction groups into normal blighting, slow blighting, and very slow blighting varieties. □

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Insect resistance

Incorporation of brown planthopper (BPH) resistance genes from indica into japonica rice

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None of the 8,200 japonica varieties or lines we screened in 1976-82 were resistant to BPH. Resistance genes can only be found in the tall traditional indica varieties of South Asia. We transferred BPH resistance genes from indica to two japonica lines (80047 and 80079) in 1980. Using those lines as resistance sources, several promising japonica lines resistant to BPH have been developed (see table).

- 864 derived from Yan Keng 2//791943/80047 yields 8 t/ha, 10% more than widely grown Yan Keng 2 and is suitable for single and double cropping in the Chang Jiang River

Yield performance and insect resistance of promising japonica lines. Jiangsu, China, 1987.

Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./plant)	Grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Resistance		
								BPH	BB	BI
864	147	100-105	9	120	8	26.0	8.0	MR	R	R
870064	155	90-95	9	146	14.2	25.3	7.9	R	R	R
850041	150	95-100	8	116	24.0	23.0	7.0	R	R	MR

basin. It is resistant to bacterial blight (BB) and moderately resistant to BPH and blast (BI). Its grain quality is acceptable to consumers.

- 870664 (Yan Keng 2//791943/80047//Non Ken 57/IR26) yields 8 t/ha and is suitable for the Tai-hu Lake basin and the

Chang Jiang River basin. It is resistant to BPH, BI, and BB.

- 850041 derived from 791943/80047 has large panicles, but unsatisfactory lodging resistance. Average yields are 7 t/ha. It is highly resistant to BPH and BB, but susceptible to sheath blight. □

Screening rice seedlings for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

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We screened 26 accessions from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project at the seedling stage for

resistance to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* in the 1987 wet season.

Pregerminated seeds were sown 6 cm apart in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. Six rows of each accession were planted across the width of the seedbox, for 3 plants/hill, 5 hills/row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and one row of resistant check Ptb 33 were sown at random in each seedbox.